

Highlights

Feature Importance Analysis of Lung Cancer Prediction Models: Consistency and Fusion

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- The consistency in the explanations provided by two feature importance techniques (specifically, LIME and SHAP) is examined for lung cancer prediction models.
- The consistency in the feature importance rankings generated by LIME and SHAP, both within the same machine learning model and between different models, is investigated.
- Inconsistencies arising from LIME and SHAP are addressed using two feature importance fusion techniques.

Feature Importance Analysis of Lung Cancer Prediction Models: Consistency and Fusion

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Abstract

The increasing use of machine learning (ML) models in cancer prediction has heightened the focus on their explainability, particularly in ranking risk factors. Although feature importance techniques like Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations (LIME) and SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) are widely used, their consistency in ranking predictive factors remains underexplored. This study examines the consistency of the explanations provided by these techniques in medical applications using UK primary care data Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD). Their consistency is assessed both within the same ML model and across different ML models for a classification task to identify lung cancer and non-lung cancer cases. The experimental results show that LIME and SHAP produce significantly different rankings even when applied to the same models. However, rankings are more consistent when the same technique is used across different models. These inconsistencies are addressed with feature importance fusion, which integrates rankings from multiple techniques within and across different models. This has been formulated as an optimisation problem and solved using a closed-form solution and a heuristic approach. The fused rankings align more closely with model-generated LIME and SHAP rankings, reducing variability across feature importance techniques and improving the overall consistency of feature importance assessments in medical applications.

Keywords: explainability, feature importance, LIME, SHAP, consistency,

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1. Introduction

Researchers have developed numerous ML models for predicting cancer risk [1, 2, 3], diagnosing cancer [4], and survival prediction [5, 6]. LIME [7] and SHAP [8] are popular techniques for interpreting these models, as noted in several studies [9, 10, 11]. However, they focus on basic applications of these explainability techniques by only reporting the rankings provided by them.

In our previous work [12], we discovered that the feature importance rankings varied even when the models performed similarly in terms of their accuracy, Area under the curve (AUC), sensitivity and specificity. This finding highlighted a noticeable gap in evaluating the consistency in the explanations provided by feature importance techniques, especially when applied to real-world medical data. Although some studies have attempted to assess the performance of these techniques [13, 14], they are often not conducted using real-world data or within medical applications.

This study aims to address the gap by examining the consistency in feature importance explanations provided by LIME and SHAP in a real-world medical application by comparing feature importance rankings of different ML models applied to CPRD data. These techniques will be implemented on widely used ML models in cancer research [15, 16, 17] for predicting lung cancer outcomes. The main contributions of this work are:

1. The consistency in the explanations of the importance of the features provided by LIME and SHAP are examined when applied to the same ML model.
2. The consistency in feature importance explanations provided by these techniques are examined when applied across different models.
3. The inconsistencies arising from these techniques are addressed with feature importance fusion by formulating an optimisation problem.

This paper is organised as follows. Section 2 discusses the widespread use of LIME and SHAP for interpreting ML models for cancer prediction studies along with existing research on evaluating the consistency of their explanations. Section 3 describes the CPRD data, predictors and models used, the methodology for assessing the consistency of LIME and SHAP and

our approach to addressing the inconsistencies from these techniques through feature importance fusion. Section 4 presents findings on the inconsistencies observed when LIME and SHAP are applied to the same lung cancer prediction models and when the same feature importance technique is applied across different models. Finally, the effectiveness of feature importance fusion in addressing these inconsistencies is demonstrated.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Popularity of LIME and SHAP for interpretability

LIME and SHAP are popular techniques for interpreting ML models in cancer prediction. To examine trends in their use, we performed a Google Scholar search using keywords such as “prediction”, “machine learning,” “cancer”, with “Shapley Additive Explanations” and “Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations” respectively. The focus was on publications since 2017, the year SHAP was introduced. Figure 1 presents a line chart showing the increasing popularity of both techniques based on this analysis. Since their development, LIME and SHAP have been referenced in over 2,500 and 6,000 publications, respectively, within cancer-related research. SHAP appears to be more widely adopted than LIME, likely due to its advanced visualisation capabilities [18]. However, there is a significant lack of research examining the consistency in explanations provided by these techniques, especially in the context of cancer data. Most existing studies have primarily focused on credit or text data instead [13, 14]. This study assesses the consistency of explanations offered by LIME and SHAP on CPRD data to determine their potential applicability in clinical settings.

2.2. Related Work

In [13], Jaccard similarity has been used to compare the top k features identified by different models and feature importance techniques. Their analysis, conducted on textual data, reveal that linear models tend to produce more similar Jaccard similarity scores compared to deep learning models. They also examine heterogeneity across instances and find that Jaccard similarity is not necessarily dependent on whether the models agree on the predicted label. In our previous work [12], this variation was highlighted, particularly noting differences in local explanations between different models when their prediction outcomes disagreed. Inconsistencies in the top k features were observed in such scenarios. In this study, we go beyond prior

Figure 1: Publications discussing LIME and SHAP in predictive ML Models in Cancer studies since 2017. Data for the line chart was obtained on 3rd February, 2025.

work by focusing on the consistency in the explanations provided by LIME and SHAP in a medical setting, specifically for lung cancer prediction models using CPRD data. Feature importance fusion is then used to reduce the inconsistencies in the feature importance rankings produced by these techniques to create robust rankings.

There has been previous work which focused on examining the stability of feature importance techniques in deep learning models. In [19], the instability of the techniques has been addressed by combining feature importance scores from different runs of a deep learning model. They demonstrate that aggregating feature importance scores from multiple high-performing models significantly enhanced stability.

Feature importance techniques have also been used as part of feature selection procedure [20, 21]. In [20], feature importance techniques, such as SHAP, permutation importance, and model-specific techniques, have been repurposed as tools for feature selection rather than interpretability. By employing a simple plurality voting approach to combine importance scores,

they demonstrate an improvement in model accuracy, demonstrating the effectiveness of feature importance fusion. Hence, examining the consistency of feature importance explanations is crucial to make correct decisions if it is to be used for feature selection during modelling.

In [22], the inconsistency of explanations provided by feature importance techniques across different ML models was highlighted, and a Python-based toolbox was proposed to fuse feature importance scores. While our work closely aligns with theirs in recognising the need for feature importance fusion, we extend the analysis by applying it to real-world medical data CPRD, ensuring that our findings are directly relevant to clinical decision making. Furthermore, rather than simply aggregating feature importance scores, we formalise the fusion process as an optimisation problem that minimises the discrepancy between individual model rankings and the fused ranking. This approach distinguishes our research by providing a practical solution using real-world medical data and by offering an optimisation framework to enhance the consistency of feature importance rankings across different models and techniques.

In [23], UK Biobank data have initially been used to show that LIME and SHAP give different results depending on the models used. They show that even when the accuracies of the models were similar, SHAP gave different feature importance rankings depending on the models. Although we established similar conclusions in our previous paper [12], this paper builds on that work by further examining the consistency in feature importance rankings through the Jaccard similarity measure. Additionally, we employ feature importance fusion, to address and resolve these inconsistencies, offering a more robust solution than what was previously explored.

Using a complementary approach, [24] interviewed 25 data scientists and academics to understand what constitutes a disagreement between different post hoc explanations. They formally defined ‘disagreement metrics’ regarding top k features to check the consistency of their explanations. Their empirical evaluation across tabular, text, and image datasets revealed that as the number of top k features increased, the disagreement between explanations also grew.

These three research studies [22, 23, 24] have significantly influenced our study, where we evaluate the consistency in feature importance rankings provided by LIME and SHAP to draw conclusions about the effectiveness of these techniques in identifying risk factors for developing lung cancer.

3. Methodology

3.1. Data

We conducted a retrospective cohort study using CPRD GOLD data [25], a real-world UK primary care data which contains anonymised patient data from general practices across the UK. CPRD contains patient information recorded by general practitioners during routine clinical visits such as demographics, diagnoses of diseases, prescriptions, etc. It covers about 4.5% of the UK population, so the data is representative of the UK population.

We examined data between January 1, 2014 and January 1, 2020. Each patient was followed from January 1, 2014. The exit date for each patient was the event which occurred the earliest - patient's death, diagnosis of lung cancer, transfer from current practice or end of the follow up period (January 1, 2020). Eligible patients were those aged between 50 and 80 years at baseline and had at least 2 years of continuous registration with their respective general practice prior to follow-up. Additionally, patients diagnosed with lung cancer within the first year of follow up were excluded to avoid ascertainment bias in the study, unlike the data used in our previous work [12]. The cohort consisted of 1,390,070 non lung cancer cases and 8,412 lung cancer cases.

3.2. Predictors

The predictors selected for this study are age, gender, smoking status and intensity, alcohol status, several comorbidities and symptoms, comprising of altogether 58 predictors. The full list of predictors can be found in Appendix A. The predictors were chosen due to being included in prior research and with the help of our clinical partners at University of Nottingham.

3.3. Feature Selection

Feature selection was performed using backward elimination with logistic regression, retaining only predictors with p-values below 0.01. Of the 58 initial predictors, 31 were excluded due to exceeding this threshold. The final set of 27 predictors included: *age, smoking status and intensity, history of bronchiectasis, history of cerebrovascular disease, history of chronic kidney disease, COPD/emphysema, diabetes with end-stage complications, diabetes without end-stage complications, family history of cancer, family history of lung cancer, idiopathic fibrosis, lower respiratory tract infections, BMI status, peptic ulcer, alcohol status, peripheral vascular disease, radio therapy,*

and personal history of *breast cancer, bladder cancer, head and neck cancer* and *thyroid cancer*. Finally, symptoms reported within the year preceding the two-year period before follow-up - *dyspnoea, haemoptysis, cough, sputum production, back pain* and any *blood test performed* - were also included.

3.4. Models

This study implemented several ML models such as Artificial Neural Network (ANN), an ensemble tree-based model eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGB) and a linear model Logistic Regression (LR), to classify between lung cancer and non-lung cancer cases. The implementation of LR was done using Scikit-learn library, ANN was implemented using Keras and XGB using [26]. The dataset was split into 80 % for training and 20 % for testing. Model training followed a similar approach to our previous work [27, 12], where an under sampling approach within an ensemble setting was used by training multiple models on different balanced subsets of the data and the final prediction was determined using a majority voting mechanism.

3.5. Feature importance techniques

This study examines the consistency of feature importance rankings provided by LIME and SHAP. This section offers a brief introduction to both techniques. For more detailed information, please refer to [28].

SHAP can interpret any model by examining both global and local feature importances. The theoretical foundation of SHAP is based on Shapley values from coalitional game theory, which allocate fair payouts when participants contribute differently in a task. In predictive tasks, each feature is analogous to a “player” in a game, and the predicted value represents the “payout”. The Shapley value is computed by determining the difference between the predicted values of a coalition with and without the features, revealing each feature’s marginal contribution. These values are then averaged across all possible feature combinations to obtain a Shapley value for each feature.

LIME employs local surrogate models to approximate the individual predictions of any black box model. The process starts by selecting a specific observation of interest. The original dataset is then perturbed to generate a new dataset with corresponding predictions. LIME subsequently trains an interpretable model, such as linear regression, where the model weights are influenced by the proximity of the perturbed samples to the observation we seek to explain.

For SHAP, the entire training dataset has been used as background data, aligning with prior research that shows SHAP yields more reliable results when provided with a large background dataset [29]. To maintain a fair comparison, the same 1,000 test data points have been used to produce the feature importance rankings for both techniques. Given that LIME provides local explanations, the absolute feature importance scores across all 1,000 test points have been averaged for each feature to obtain a global estimate of overall feature importance.

3.6. Checking consistency in feature importance explanations

We examine whether models trained on the same dataset provide consistent explanations using LIME and SHAP. The following questions are addressed:

1. Are features consistently ranked in the top k across LIME and SHAP for the same models?
2. Are features consistently ranked in the top k across different models when using the same feature importance technique?

The Jaccard similarity measure has been used to compare the top k features produced by LIME and SHAP to assess whether these features consistently rank in the top k across different models and feature importance techniques. Given two explanations E_A and E_B , the Jaccard similarity is defined as:

$$\text{Jaccard similarity}(E_A, E_B) = \frac{|\text{Top}(E_A, k) \cap \text{Top}(E_B, k)|}{|\text{Top}(E_A, k) \cup \text{Top}(E_B, k)|}, \quad (1)$$

where $\text{Top}(E, k)$ denotes the set of top k features of explanation E and $|\cdot|$ denotes the cardinality of the set.

Furthermore, a quartile based analysis is performed [29] to determine whether a U-shaped distribution emerges between the Jaccard similarity of feature rankings produced by LIME and SHAP.

Let us illustrate how to calculate the Jaccard similarity with a hypothetical example. Consider two ordered rankings: Ranking 1 = {a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j} and Ranking 2 = {a, c, e, g, i, k, m, n, o, p}. First, identify the common elements between the two sets. The intersection of Ranking 1 and Ranking 2 is {a, c, e, g, i}, which contains 5 elements. The union of the rankings has 15 elements. Therefore, the Jaccard similarity calculated using Equation (1) is 1/3.

3.7. Address inconsistencies with feature importance fusion

The inconsistencies in feature importance rankings produced by LIME and SHAP are addressed through feature importance fusion. Feature importance fusion [22] is an approach used to aggregate feature importance scores obtained from multiple models and feature importance techniques to achieve a more stable and reliable interpretation of feature relevance. This approach addresses the inconsistencies observed when various ML models or feature importance techniques assign different levels of importance to the same features, particularly in complex, real-world datasets, as we will see in Section 4.2 and 4.3.

To determine the optimal fusion of feature importance rankings, an optimisation problem is formulated. Given n models $\{M_i, i = 1, \dots, n\}$ and m features $\{f_j, j = 1, \dots, m\}$, each model M_i assigns either a ranking or importance score to the m features. The rankings can be represented by a feature ranking vector:

$$\vec{FI}_i = (R_i(f_1), \dots, R_i(f_m)),$$

where $R_i(f_j)$ represents the rank of feature f_j assigned by model M_i . Alternatively, if the model assigns importance scores instead of ranks, then $\vec{FI}_i(f_j)$ represents the importance score.

The optimal fusion \vec{Fu} is defined as the fused ranking that minimises the total distance between itself and each individual model ranking. Specifically, $d_i(\vec{FI}_i, \vec{Fu})$ represents the distance between \vec{FI}_i and the fused ranking \vec{Fu} . This optimisation problem can be formulated as:

$$\min_{\vec{Fu}} \sum_{i=1}^n d_i(\vec{FI}_i, \vec{Fu}). \quad (2)$$

If the distance is chosen to be the squared Euclidean distance defined as:

$$d_i(\vec{FI}_i, \vec{Fu}) = \sum_{j=1}^m (FI_i(f_j) - Fu(f_j))^2 \quad \text{where } i = 1, \dots, n. \quad (3)$$

Minimising the total squared Euclidean distance across all models leads to the following optimisation problem:

$$\min_{\vec{Fu}} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m (FI_i(f_j) - Fu(f_j))^2. \quad (4)$$

The arithmetic mean minimises the sum of squared Euclidean distances. Thus, the optimal fused ranking $\vec{F}u$ is given by the element-wise average across all model feature importance scores:

$$\vec{F}u = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \vec{F}I_i. \quad (5)$$

Alternatively, if the Jaccard distance[30] is used, it is defined as:

$$d_i(\vec{F}I_i, \vec{F}u) = 1 - \text{Jaccard similarity}(\vec{F}I_i, \vec{F}u) \quad \text{where } i = 1, \dots, n. \quad (6)$$

where $\text{Jaccard similarity}(\vec{F}I_i, \vec{F}u)$ measures the overlap between the fused ranking $\vec{F}u$ and the ranking $\vec{F}I_i$ from model M_i . The optimal fused ranking $\vec{F}u$ is determined by minimising the total Jaccard distance across all models as given in Equation (2), where d_i is defined as in Equation (6). Since Jaccard distance and Jaccard similarity are inversely related, this is equivalent to maximising the total Jaccard similarity across all models [31].

A heuristic approach is taken to approximate the optimal fusion $\vec{F}u$ that maximises the Jaccard similarity by aggregating feature rankings using Borda count [32, 33]. This method is widely used in electoral polls where multiple candidates can be ranked rather than voting for a single candidate. It is optimal under the Jaccard distance because, unlike plurality voting, it maximises the overall similarity between the aggregated feature rankings and the individual rankings by considering the relative positions of all features. We demonstrate empirically that the Borda count method helps maximise Jaccard similarity across feature importance rankings from multiple models.

The Borda count method assigns a ‘score’ to each feature based on its position in each ranking. The lower the rank (i.e., the higher the importance), the higher the score. This process results in a more globally consistent ranking by counting how often a feature appears in ranks across multiple techniques. For each feature f_j , the Borda score is defined as:

$$\text{Borda}(f_j) = \sum_{i=1}^n (\text{max_features} - \text{rank}_{M_i}(f_j)) \quad (7)$$

where $\text{max_features} = m$ is the total number of features and $\text{rank}_{M_i}(f_j)$ is the rank of feature f_j in the i -th models’ M_i ranking. The features are then ranked according to their total Borda scores. The feature with the highest

Borda score is ranked first (most important), while the one with the lowest score is ranked last (least important).

Figure 2 presents the procedure used to address the inconsistencies introduced by feature importance techniques through the use of feature importance fusion.

Figure 2: Strategy to reduce inconsistencies introduced by feature importance techniques using feature importance fusion. While this paper only use LIME and SHAP for feature importance fusion, the approach can be extended to incorporate any number of models and feature importance techniques as shown in the figure.

4. Results

In this section, the consistency in feature importance rankings provided by LIME and SHAP across different models and within the same feature importance technique have been evaluated using the Jaccard similarity measure. The inconsistencies observed are then addressed by using feature importance fusion.

4.1. Explainability using LIME and SHAP

The top 10 features for predicting lung cancer risk obtained from LIME and SHAP for all three models using CPRD data are presented in Figures 3 and 4, respectively. The top 10 features differ between the feature importance techniques and models. Features *age* and *smoking status and intensity* consistently appear in the top two for predicting lung cancer for both XGB and LR when using SHAP. In contrast, LIME ranks *dyspnoea* above *smoking status and intensity* for XGB and above *age* for both LR and ANN, with *age* not even appearing in the top 10 for ANN. Beyond these top two predictors, there is significant inconsistency in feature rankings across models, with some features appearing in the top 10 for one technique but not the other. For example, SHAP lists features *COPD/emphysema* and *BMI Status* in the top 10 for XGB but not for LR, while *cough* and *diabetes with end stage complications* appear for LR but not for XGB. Similarly, in LIME, features like *COPD/emphysema*, *haemoptysis*, *head and neck cancer*, and *thyroid cancer* are among the top 10 for XGB but absent in LR, whereas *breast cancer*, *chronic kidney disease*, *diabetes with end-stage complications*, and *radio therapy* are not present in XGB but are included in LR.

4.2. Consistency in explanations using different feature importance techniques on the same models

The Jaccard similarity measure has been used to assess the consistency of feature importance rankings produced by LIME and SHAP when applied to the same models. As shown in Figure 5, the alignment is highest in the first quartile across all models, with XGB and LR sharing the most predictors between LIME and SHAP in this quartile. For ANN, similarity decreases in the second quartile, remains nearly unchanged in the third, and increases in the fourth, displaying an approximate U-shaped pattern. XGB exhibits an upward trend in the third quartile but shares no features in the fourth. These findings highlight the importance of examining consistency in feature importance rankings across different quartiles, particularly when working with a large number of features where inconsistencies can be more pronounced [24].

4.3. Consistency in explanations using the same feature importance technique

The feature importance rankings obtained were more consistent across models using the same feature importance technique, as shown in Figure 6. SHAP demonstrated higher consistency, particularly between XGB and LR,

Figure 3: Top 10 features derived from LIME for XGB, LR, and ANN Models.

which shared over 75% of features in the first quartile. In contrast, LIME showed lower alignment, with XGB and LR sharing only about 55% of features in the same quartile. SHAP's Jaccard similarity across models generally followed a U-shaped pattern, with high feature overlap in the first and fourth quartiles, while LIME exhibited more variability in feature rankings.

Figure 4: Top 10 features derived from SHAP for XGB, LR, and ANN Models.

4.4. Addressing inconsistencies in explanations with feature importance fusion

We address the inconsistencies in feature importance rankings produced by LIME and SHAP using feature importance fusion discussed in Section 3.7. This process is carried out in two stages:

1. Combine rankings obtained within each feature importance technique to minimise the squared Euclidean distance or Jaccard distance between the models' rankings and fused rankings.
2. Combine rankings obtained from different feature importance techniques for the same models to minimise the distance between the models' rankings and fused rankings.

Figure 5: Jaccard similarity of feature rankings between LIME and SHAP across quartiles for XGB, LR and ANN

4.4.1. Fusion within the same feature importance technique

The rankings obtained from each feature importance technique are combined to minimise the squared Euclidean distance between the individual models' rankings and the fused rankings. To achieve this, within each feature importance technique (SHAP and LIME), the following steps are carried out for each model (XGB, LR and ANN):

1. Rank features according to their importance scores within each model.
2. For each feature, determine its most common rank across the models and calculate the average importance score for that rank. If no common rank exists, the average for that feature is computed using all importance scores from the different models.
3. Sort features by their averaged coefficients to generate the final ranking.

This approach generates combined rankings for SHAP and LIME separately, as shown in Figures 7 and 8. By doing this, feature *age* appears in the top 10 rankings for both LIME and SHAP, aligning with clinical expectations [34]. This is particularly noteworthy given that *age* was initially absent from the top 10 rankings for ANN. The inclusion of this clinically relevant feature after fusion suggests that the aggregation process enhances the robustness of feature importance rankings, ensuring that key domain-specific variables are

Figure 6: Comparative analysis of Jaccard similarity measure in feature rankings across Quartiles for LIME and SHAP.

appropriately prioritised.

To minimise the Jaccard distance, feature rankings are aggregated using the Borda count method, as described in Section 3.7. The comparison of the top 10 ranked features, obtained through the Borda count method for LIME and SHAP are shown in Figures 9 and 10 respectively in the form of heatmaps. Similarly, after applying the Borda count method, the feature *age* consistently appears in the top 10 rankings for both LIME and SHAP, even though it was initially absent in the rankings derived from ANN. This

Figure 7: Top 10 feature rankings obtained by averaging feature importance scores from LIME across XGB, LR, and ANN models.

inclusion aligns with clinical expectations, which reinforces the reliability of this aggregation approach.

Furthermore, the heatmaps in Figures 9 and 10 show a strong similarity between the fused rankings and the individual rankings obtained from LIME and SHAP across all three models (XGB, LR, and ANN). To confirm this similarity, Jaccard similarity scores are computed, as shown in Figure 11. The results indicate that for SHAP, LR shows the highest Jaccard similarity in the first and fourth quartiles when fused with Borda count, sharing identical features in those quartiles. In the case of LIME, XGB and LR demonstrate the highest alignment, sharing approximately 75% of features. Overall, the Jaccard similarity is higher for SHAP compared to LIME. The fusion approach using the Borda count method significantly improves Jaccard similarity scores compared to Figures 5 and 6, where LIME and SHAP

Figure 8: Top 10 feature rankings obtained by averaging feature importance scores from SHAP across XGB, LR, and ANN models..

were applied to each model independently. This highlights the effectiveness of the Borda count method in maximising Jaccard similarity by aligning the fused rankings more closely with individual model rankings.

4.4.2. Fusion across different feature importance techniques

For completeness, the fusion method is performed across different feature importance techniques for each model separately. To integrate scores from different feature importance techniques, the feature importance scores obtained from all three models are normalised, and the following steps are carried out:

1. Normalise feature importance scores from each feature importance technique to a common scale to account for differences in scoring between LIME and SHAP.

Figure 9: Comparison of Top 10 feature rankings using Borda count with LIME vs Models rankings.

Figure 10: Comparison of Top 10 feature rankings using Borda count with SHAP vs Models rankings.

Figure 11: Jaccard Similarity of Feature Rankings Across Quartiles: Models vs. Fusion for LIME and SHAP.

2. Calculate the average normalised importance scores for each feature.
3. Rank features by their averaged scores to produce the final ranking.

The fusion across feature importance techniques is performed independently for XGB, LR and ANN, with combined results presented in Figure 12. This approach aggregates the feature importance scores from LIME and SHAP for all models independently. Features *age* and *smoking status and intensity* appear in the top 10 rankings for all three models, which aligns with clinical expectations. Similar patterns were observed when fusion was conducted within the same feature importance technique in Section 4.4.1, which shows the effectiveness of our approach. These findings further support the conclusion that feature importance fusion, formulated as an optimisation problem, enhances the consistency in ranking predictive factors.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

In this study, the consistency in the explanations provided by LIME and SHAP in terms of ranking features for lung cancer prediction models are examined, using CPRD data. The findings showed that the agreement between LIME and SHAP rankings was strongest in the first quartile across all models, but there was a decline in the subsequent quartiles, indicating that different feature importance techniques tend to disagree most on the least important features. To address these inconsistencies, an optimisation problem was formulated to reduce the discrepancy in rankings. When using the squared Euclidean distance, the optimal solution was the average of feature importance rankings across all models. Alternatively, with Jaccard distance, a heuristic approach was employed using the Borda count method to minimise ranking disparities. The fused feature rankings from LIME and SHAP confirmed that features *age* and *smoking status and intensity* consistently ranked among the top five predictors for lung cancer risk, aligning well with clinical expectations. Therefore, framing feature importance fusion as an optimisation problem significantly improves the consistency in ranking predictive factors.

There are several limitations to this study. LIME did not produce clinically relevant results despite using the same test data points as SHAP, although this was resolved when fusion was applied. While a random seed was set to ensure consistency in both feature importance techniques, repeating the analysis across multiple runs could enhance robustness [35]. However,

Figure 12: Top 10 rankings obtained with normalisation of feature importance scores from LIME and SHAP for XGB, LR and ANN.

due to computational constraints, this was not explored in this study. The default kernel width for LIME was used, although prior research [14] has

shown that explanation stability is sensitive to this parameter. Future work could investigate the impact of different kernel widths on LIME's reliability. While Jaccard similarity was used to measure inconsistencies, incorporating additional metrics could provide a more comprehensive evaluation of explanation stability [36]. In [23], the problem arising with LIME and SHAP due to using multicollinear features is explored. Our future work will focus on how this issue may affect our results on the CPRD data for predicting lung cancer risk, and potentially explain why *age* was not in the top 10 rankings for LIME and SHAP for ANN because *age* is highly correlated with many other features in the dataset.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Rai: Writing - original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualisation. He: Writing - review and editing, Conceptualisation, Methodology, Supervision, Project administration. Kaur: Data curation. Shen: Writing - review and editing, Methodology. Mahmud: Writing - review and editing, Conceptualisation, Supervision. Brown: Writing - review and editing, Conceptualisation, Supervision, Resources. O'Dowd: Conceptualisation, Resources. Baldwin: Conceptualisation, Resources.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data and code availability

Data used in this work is available through CPRD and is not publicly available. See <https://www.cprd.com/data-access> for more details. The code of this study can be available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author.

Ethics

Approval for the use of data for this work was granted by the CPRD Independent Scientific Advisory Committee (ISAC) (Protocol number 20_014R).

Declaration of generative AI in writing

The AI tool Writefull in Overleaf was used.

Appendix A. List of predictors

1. Age
2. Smoking status and intensity
3. Body Mass Index (BMI)
4. Alcohol status
5. Gender
6. Exposure to Asbestosis
7. History of bronchiectasis
8. Cerebrovascular disease
9. Chronic Kidney Disease
10. Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)/emphysema
11. Connective Tissue
12. Dementia
13. Diabetes with no end-stage complications
14. Diabetes with end stage complications
15. Family history of lung cancer
16. Family history of cancer (excluding lung cancer)
17. Hypertension
18. Hemiplegia
19. Idiopathic Fibrosis

20. Lower Respiratory Tract Infections
21. Lymphoma
22. Mid Liver Disease
23. Moderate Liver disease
24. Myocardial infraction + ischaemic heart disease
25. Osteoarthritis
26. Peptic Ulcer
27. Pneumonia
28. Pulmonary Tuberculosis
29. Peripheral Vascular Disease
30. Rheumatoid Arthritis
31. Radio Therapy
32. Personal history of cancers
 - (a) Head and neck Cancer
 - (b) Bladder Cancer
 - (c) Breast Cancer
 - (d) Thyroid Cancer
 - (e) Prostate Cancer
 - (f) Bowel Cancer
 - (g) Thyroid Cancer
 - (h) Stomach Cancer
 - (i) Kidney Cancer
 - (j) Ovary cancer
 - (k) Leukemia
 - (l) Myeloma
 - (m) Melanoma
 - (n) Pancreatic Cancer
 - (o) Oesophagus Cancer
33. Symptoms:
 - (a) Dyspnoea
 - (b) Blood test
 - (c) Cough
 - (d) Haemoptysis
 - (e) Back Pain
 - (f) Sputum
 - (g) Chest and shoulder pain
 - (h) Any Chest X-ray done
 - (i) Spirometry Test
 - (j) Voice hoarseness
 - (k) Weightloss
34. History of substance abuse

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